

Spectrum of Late Toxicity of Radiotherapy in Head and Neck Cancer Patients

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Abstract

Background: Radiotherapy remains a fundamental treatment modality for head and neck cancer. This study aimed to assess the range, frequency, and severity of late radiation-induced effects in head and neck cancer survivors. **Methods:** This cross-sectional study conducted at the Department of Radiation Oncology, Cancer Center, CMH, Dhaka, from September 2024 to February 2025, included patients with histopathologically diagnosed stage I-III locally advanced head & neck cancer receiving radiotherapy. A sample size of 63 was used, and a convenience sampling method was employed. **Results:** Among 63 patients, 84.0% were male, 52.0% were aged ≤ 60 years, and 46.0% had an ECOG PS of 2. Radiotherapy was delivered using VMAT, IMRT and 3DCRT in 70.0%, 24.0%, and 6.0% of cases. Most common late radiation sequelae based on RTOG grading scale was found salivary gland toxicities, with 70% experiencing various grades of dysphagia. With the CTCAE grading scale, apart from xerostomia, dental caries was 28.57% trismus and aspiration was 34.9%. Dysphagia prevalence was 77.77% and xerostomia was 79.36% at 4 months of follow-up. Statistically significant association was present between diagnosis and xerostomia also dysphagia at 4 months follow-up. **Conclusion:** Radiotherapy holds a crucial position in the treatment of head and neck cancer. However, since no technology can completely shield healthy tissues from exposure, it is essential to take every precaution to limit radiation doses to normal tissues through both preventive and supportive strategies.

Introduction

Radiotherapy holds a crucial position in treating head and neck malignancies, the second most common cancer among males in Bangladesh. The conventional therapeutic approach for locally advanced head and neck squamous cell carcinoma (LAHNSCC) integrates surgery, radiation therapy (RT), and chemotherapy [1-2]. Over recent decades, survival rates for individuals with head and neck cancer (HNC) have markedly increased due to more intensive treatment protocols and a growing incidence of Human Papillomavirus (HPV)-related oropharyngeal carcinoma, which generally has a more favorable prognosis [3-4]. As patient survival extends, minimizing therapy-induced adverse effects that impact quality of life and daily activities has gained greater importance. Radiotherapy for people with head and neck cancers can cause various complications which can sometimes

be severe especially when it is given together with chemotherapy [5,6]. These are categorized into acute and late toxicities. Acute reactions involve damage occurring from the first day of treatment until day 90, whereas late or chronic radiation-induced effects appear beyond day 90 and may persist indefinitely [7]. This classification has been formalized by the European Organization for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC) and the Radiation Therapy Oncology Group (RTOG), which developed the LENT-SOMA scale (Late Effects of Normal Tissues – Subjective, Objective, Management, Analytic) to evaluate both early and delayed consequences of therapy [8,9]. Since the probability of radiation-induced toxicity is mainly influenced by the dose delivered to nearby organs at risk (OAR), limiting radiation exposure to these structures while preserving tumor control is critical [10].

More Information

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organs at risk.

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Recent technological advancements have greatly improved dose distribution accuracy, reducing exposure to specific OAR [11,12]. However, completely avoiding radiation to these structures remains impossible, and in many cases, protecting some OAR leads to increased exposure to others [13]. In modern clinical practice, treatment planning is guided by standardized dose limitations, often derived from QUANTEC guidelines, applied to a limited number of OAR in all patients to mitigate specific toxicities [14-15]. To better address the complexity of toxicity prevention and utilize new technologies, this traditional method should evolve into a more personalized approach that aims to minimize radiation to all essential OAR, not just a few.

To achieve the ideal balance between tumor control and toxicity reduction, extensive data on the relationship between normal tissue irradiation and complication probability is crucial. Normal Tissue Complication Probability (NTCP) models quantify these relationships and support decision-making by identifying optimal dose distributions for each patient [16-18]. However, for many toxicities, robust NTCP models incorporating key OAR and accurate dose-response data remain unavailable. Many existing models also do not align with OAR definitions in international guidelines [19] and lack external validation [20], limiting their clinical applicability [21-22].

Ionizing radiation primarily causes single- and double-strand breaks in DNA and alters the cellular microenvironment via reactive oxygen species, resulting in partial apoptosis [23]. Rapidly proliferating tissues like skin and mucosa respond with acute inflammation. In tissues with slower turnover, DNA damage and micro environmental changes still occur, but are not mainly driven by cell division. Instead, chemokines and inflammatory and fibrotic cytokines regulate intercellular interactions and migration, causing delayed injury like fibrosis, atrophy, or vascular damage [24]. Thrombotic and ischemic complications may also arise [25].

So far, no link has been found between the severity of acute effects such as radio dermatitis or mucositis and late toxicities like fibrosis. Individual variations in radiotherapy response are attributed to genetic differences in DNA repair, inflammation, apoptosis, and cell proliferation [26]. With more head and neck cancer survivors, a growing range of long-term radiotherapy effects is being seen. Radiation-induced toxicities harm quality of life, with xerostomia, dysphagia, radiation caries, trismus, and osteoradionecrosis being most common. As life expectancy rises, reducing treatment-related toxicities that hinder daily life is increasingly important [27].

Numerous international studies have identified advanced age, progressive disease, laryngeal and pharyngeal involvement, concurrent chemotherapy, accelerated hyperfractionation, and short interfraction intervals as key risk factors for chronic toxicity. However, data on late radiation complications among Bangladeshi head and neck cancer survivors are scarce. Therefore, we conducted this study to assess the incidence of late xerostomia, dysphagia, fibrosis, trismus, osteoradionecrosis, and radiation caries at 6-month, 1-year, and 2-year intervals from the start of radiotherapy, evaluate toxicity severity, and describe the sociodemographic characteristics of respondents.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted at the Department of Radiation Oncology, Cancer Centre, Combined Military Hospital (CMH), Dhaka, following approval by the Clinical Research Ethical Committee of CMH Dhaka. The study was carried out from September 2024 to February 2025.

Study Population and Sampling

The study population comprised patients with histopathologically confirmed Stage I-III locally advanced head and neck squamous cell carcinoma who had completed radiotherapy at the study centre. A convenient sampling method was employed, with an estimated minimum sample size of 60. Participants were recruited from patients attending follow-up visits at the outpatient clinic of the Department of Radiation Oncology.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria required a diagnosis of Stage I-III squamous cell carcinoma of the oral cavity, oropharynx, nasopharynx, hypopharynx, or larynx. Eligible patients must have received primary radiotherapy, either as a standalone treatment or concurrently with chemotherapy, and have an Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group (ECOG) performance status of 1 or 2. Exclusion criteria were defined as follows: prior surgical intervention for head and neck cancer (excluding laser resection of small glottic lesions); no previous oncological treatment; the presence of synchronous tumors outside the head and neck region; receipt of a radiotherapy fraction dose exceeding 2.2 Gy; and patient withdrawal of consent.

Data Collection and Variables

All late toxicity sequelae were documented in accordance with the study protocol and graded using the Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (CTCAE), version 5.0.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS software (version 26.0). Categorical variables were summarized using frequency tables and percentages. Associations between variables were assessed using non-parametric tests,

primarily the Chi-square test. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 63 patients were enrolled in the study, of whom approximately half (52%) were aged 60 years or younger (Figure 1), and the majority (84%) were male (Figure 2), with an ECOG PS of 2 in 46.0% of patients and 3 in 34.9%. 1 and 0 in 9.5%. Among 63 patients, stage III cases were 54.0%, 30.0% were stage II, and 16.0% were stage I. 44.4% were moderately differentiated, 28.6% were well differentiated, 20.6%

poorly differentiated, and 6.3% were undifferentiated carcinoma.

The prevalent late radiation sequelae in our study, based on the RTOG grading scale, were found to be salivary gland toxicities, 70% experienced various grades of dysphagia. With the CTCAE grading scale, apart from xerostomia, dental caries was 28.57% trismus and aspiration was 34.9%. Dysphagia prevalence was 77.77% and xerostomia was 79.36% at 4 months of follow-up. (Table 1)

Table 1: Incidence and Severity of Late Toxicities in Different Follow-Ups

Late toxicities	Incidence (any grade)	Grade 3	Grade 2	Grade 1
Xerostomia				
4 months	79.36 (50/63)	6	19	25
10 months	39.7 (25/63)	2	2	21
1.5 years	28.6 (18/63)	1	1	16
2 years	23.8 (15/63)	1	1	13
Dysphagia				
4 months	77.77 (49/63)	8	21	20
10 months	27.0 (17/63)	1	2	14
1.5 years	22.2 (14/63)	1	1	12
2 years	12.7 (8/63)	0	1	7
Aspiration				
4 months	34.9 (22/63)	3	4	15
10 months	17.5 (11/63)	1	2	8
1.5 years	11.1 (7/63)	0	1	6
2 years	3.2 (2/63)	0	0	2
Osteoradionecrosis				
4 months	(0/63)	0	0	0
10 months	(0/63)	0	0	0
1.5 years	1.58 (1/63)	0	0	1
2 years	1.58 (1/63)	0	0	1
Trismus				
4 months	34.9 (22/63)	4	5	13
10 months	20.63 (13/63)	2	3	9
1.5 years	14.28 (9/63)	1	2	6
2 years	19.04 (12/63)	1	3	5
Dental caries				
4 months	28.57 (38/63)	3	12	23
10 months	25.39 (16/63)	1	4	11
1.5 years	23.80 (15/63)	1	3	11
2 years	11.11 (07/63)	0	2	5

Table 1 shows the most common late toxicities at 4 months were xerostomia (79.4%) and dysphagia (77.8%), which decreased both in incidence and severity over the 2-year follow-up period. Aspiration, trismus, and dental caries were present in a moderate number of patients at 4 months (28.6-34.9%) and also showed a general trend of resolution over time.

Osteoradionecrosis was rare, appearing in only one patient (1.6%) after 1.5 years. Notably, the incidence of trismus showed a slight increase at the 2-year mark (19.0%) compared to the 1.5-year assessment (14.3%). Data are presented as incidence percentage with raw data (n/N) and the number of patients for each toxicity grade.

Figure 1: Distribution of Respondents by Age Category (n=63)

Figure 1 illustrates that half of the patients (52%) were aged up to 60 years.

Figure 2: Distribution of Respondents by Gender (n=63)

Figure 2 depicts that the majority (84%) were male patients.

Figure 3: Distribution of Respondents by Diagnosis (n=63)

It was observed that 60% cases comprised either carcinoma larynx or oropharynx demonstrated by Figure 3.

Figure 4: Distribution of Respondents by Radiotherapy Modality

A lion’s share of (70%) patients received radiotherapy by VMAT.

Table 2 shows the association between diagnosis and xerostomia at 4 months follow-up. Chi-square value was 28.01, degree of differentiation 12 and p-value was 0.005, which is statistically significant.

Table 2: Association between Diagnosis and Xerostomia at 4 Months Follow-Up

Diagnosis	No Xerostomia	Mild Xerostomia	Moderate Xerostomia	Severe Xerostomia	Total
Ca oral cavity	0 (0%)	2 (28.6%)	3 (42.9%)	2 (28.6%)	7 (100%)
Ca oropharynx	1 (4.5%)	4 (18.2%)	10 (45.5%)	07 (31.8%)	42 (100%)
Ca larynx	5 (21.7%)	16 (69.6%)	02 (8.7%)	0 (0.0%)	43 (100%)
Nasopharynx	1 (20.0%)	3 (60.0%)	1 (20.0%)	0 (0.0%)	5 (100%)
Hypopharynx	3 (50.0%)	0 (0.0%)	3 (50.0%)	0 (0.0%)	6 (100%)
Total	10 (15.9%)	25 (39.7%)	19 (30.2%)	09 (14.3%)	63 (100%)

Note: χ^2 (df) =28.01 (12), p = 0.005

Correlating the late toxicities with variables of primary tumor site, ECOG performance status, and composite stage, it was observed that xerostomia was more prevalent in survivors with primary tumor site in oropharynx and larynx in comparison with other head and neck subsites (*P* value 0.005) (Table 2). Dysphagia

was observed significantly more in survivors of laryngeal cancer (*P* value 0.02) followed by oropharynx, but it also reached statistical significance (Table 3). Trismus and osteoradionecrosis were more in the larynx followed by oropharynx and ca tongue but this was not significant (Table 4).

Table 3: Association between Diagnosis and Dysphagia at 4 Months Follow-Up

Diagnosis	No Dysphagia	Mild Dysphagia	Moderate Dysphagia	Severe Dysphagia	Total
Ca Oral cavity	5 (71.4%)	1 (14.3%)	0 (12.5%)	1 (14.3%)	7 (100%)
Ca oropharynx	2 (9.1%)	6 (27.3%)	8 (36.4%)	6 (27.3%)	22 (100%)
Ca larynx	3 (13.0%)	8 (34.8%)	8 (34.8%)	4 (17.4%)	23 (100%)
Ca Nasopharynx	0 (0%)	2 (40.0%)	3 (60.0%)	0 (0%)	5 (100%)
Ca Hypopharynx	0 (0%)	3 (50.0%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.7%)	6 (100%)
Total	10 (15.9%)	20 (31.7%)	21 (33.3%)	12 (19.0%)	63 (100.0%)

Note: χ^2 (df) = 23.22 (12), *p* = 0.02

Table 3 lists the association between diagnosis and dysphagia at 4 months of follow-up. Chi-square value

was 23.22, degree of differentiation 12 *p*-value was 0.02, which is statistically significant.

Table 4: Association between Diagnosis and Trismus at 4 Months Follow-Up

Diagnosis	No Trismus	Mild Trismus	Moderate Trismus	Severe Trismus	Total
Ca oral cavity	4 (57.1%)	1 (14.3%)	1 (14.3%)	1 (14.3%)	7 (100.0%)
Ca oropharynx	10 (45.5%)	8 (36.4%)	3 (13.6%)	1 (4.5%)	22 (100.0%)
Ca larynx	6 (26.1%)	12 (52.2%)	5 (21.7%)	0 (0.0%)	23 (100.0%)
Ca Nasopharynx	1 (20.0%)	3 (60.5%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (20.0%)	5 (100.0%)
Ca Hypopharynx	3 (50.0%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (16.7%)	6 (100.0%)
Total	24 (38.1%)	26 (41.3%)	9 (14.3%)	4 (6.3%)	63 (100.0%)

Note: χ^2 (df)=12.259 (12), *p*=0.42

Table 4 shows association between diagnosis and trismus at 4 months follow-up. Among 63 respondents severe trismus developed in 4 cases. Chi-square value was 12.25 degree of differentiation 12 *p*-value was 0.42 which was not statistically significant.

Among other late toxicities, pain, subcutaneous fibrosis and neck oedema were observed in 9, 23 patients, and 7 patients, respectively. only 1 patient was reported with osteoradionecrosis and the patient was a case of recurrent laryngeal carcinoma.

Discussion

Radiation, acting as both a vital tool and a potential risk in the multimodal management of head and neck cancers, can cause adverse effects that diminish the quality of life in survivors. In our study, the majority of patients received VMAT rather than 3DCRT with parotid preservation, leading to a lower incidence of xerostomia.

The recorded incidence of dental caries according to CTCAE grading in our study was 28.57%, which is consistent with the incidence of dental caries in patients with head and neck cancer post-radiotherapy

observed to be approximately 29%, based on a meta-analysis of 15 studies. [28].

Trismus, or restricted jaw mobility, arises due to fibrosis of the underlying tissues and muscles surrounding the temporomandibular joint following radiation therapy. A study by Geer et al. [29] documented a prevalence of 23.6% among head and neck cancer survivors who had undergone radiotherapy. In our study, the prevalence of trismus was recorded at 17%, with 13% classified as grade 1 and 4% as grade 2.

Dysphagia is another frequently observed late-stage complication induced by radiation among survivors. The dysfunction related to dysphagia aspiration-related structures (DARS) [30]. A study conducted in Australia by Frowen et al. [31] reported a dysphagia incidence of up to 55%, with 20% of cases involving difficulty swallowing liquids and 46% encountering challenges with solid foods. In our study, dysphagia was detected in 45% of the participants, with 38% experiencing symptoms while still being able to maintain a normal diet.

Appropriate management of such toxicities is crucial for physicians while treating chronic conditions such as

cancer. The results outline major toxic effects of long-standing radiotherapy and provide key insights on the severity of such effects. This may benefit patients and prescribers both in deciding further treatment strategy simultaneously aid in improving the patients' quality of life by relieving symptoms.

One of the primary limitations of this research is the limited sample size, along with a short and inconsistent follow-up period. As a result, the development of comprehensive databases with extended follow-up durations and detailed treatment variables is crucial for enhancing our understanding of these late-onset complications.

Conclusion

Radiotherapy holds a crucial position in the comprehensive treatment of over half of all individuals with head and neck cancer, contributing to more than 40% of successful recoveries. Innovations in radiation planning and equipment have significantly diminished the most concerning adverse effects, enhancing the quality of life for survivors. However, since no technology can completely shield healthy tissues from exposure, it is essential to take every precaution to limit radiation doses to normal tissues through both preventive and supportive strategies

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Informed Consent Statement

Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study.

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